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Table of Content

1	<i>Introduction</i>	3
2	<i>Management aspects of access</i>	3
3	<i>Policy and legal aspects of access</i>	5
4	<i>Financial aspects of access</i>	6
5	<i>Concluding remarks</i>	8
6.	<i>References</i>	8

1 Introduction

Research Infrastructures (RIs) play a critical role in advancing scientific knowledge and fostering innovation by providing access -physical, remote, hybrid or virtual- to world-class facilities. This document is a final deliverable of WP1: Developing the concept and guidelines for physical access to distributed atmospheric Research Infrastructures, summarising the results and recommendations from the Deliverables 1.1 [1], Deliverable 1.2 [2] and 1.3 [3].

The overall goal of WP1 was to analyse the legal and financial aspects governing access to atmospheric facilities and services, and to incorporate these elements into an optimal and synergistic access framework embedded in recommendations and guidelines applicable to distributed research infrastructure access services. The purpose of this document is to give an overview of the WP1 results, targeted at research infrastructures providing access to wide user groups.

2 Management aspects of access

Task 1.1 and the resulting Deliverable 1.1 provided insight into the common access management concept for distributed RIs in the atmospheric domain. This common concept for access management is a component of a broader strategic framework for access. The common access management concept and access procedures are a result of the joint efforts to harmonise and streamline the process of accessing facilities and services between the atmospheric RIs.

A harmonised access management system strengthens the research network, promotes international collaboration, to better exploit the facilities, share knowledge and resources, and develop excellent science. A common access management concept directly benefits the users, the providers, and the involved RIs by making the access provision simpler, more effective, and more robust, eventually increasing both the number of users and scientific excellence.

The following elements can be identified as key components of the common access management concept:

1. Harmonised access and data policies
2. Well-structured and well-defined Access management plan and Data management plan
3. Common access programme
4. Shared management principles supporting cross-RI access services
5. Unique entry point for the users and harmonised access procedures, supporting efficient access management, especially in distributed RIs
6. Common tools for centralised management (catalogue of services, interactive access management platform, user helpdesk, etc.)

7. Common strategies for communication, user attraction and engagement, based on the communication policy and user policy of each RI

All seven elements were carefully studied and analysed in task 1.1 and implemented in task 9.1 and, therefore, stand as tested, accepted and recommended for the common access management concept of the distributed atmospheric RIs.

In addition to the components presented above, certain recommendations have been made to address identified issues and ensure further improvements of the access programme. These include:

1. harmonisation of service provision management to provide the user with the general performance standards of the facility, i.e. what the user can expect from the facility with respect to the practicalities of the access provision
2. Effective and timely planning of the opening and closing of access calls
3. streamlining and ensuring an efficient access process for the private sector
4. potential centralisation of the financial management of the access provision
5. ensuring that the common access management concept is also effectively applied to the national access
6. developing and maintaining a catalogue of services, easily findable and accessible, and explorable by users
7. easily accessible user helpdesk to support users in finding, requesting, and accessing the required resources
8. development of tools to easily harvest the user and provider statistics and other key performance indicators, supporting the monitoring and reporting of access activities
9. continuous evaluation and adjustment of the process as necessary, responding to user and provider feedback

It is acknowledged that the implementation of the common access management concept can be challenging due to various aspects of individual RIs such as the specificities of the access provision, variability and sustainability of funding and other resources and other organisational and operational limitations. Nevertheless, the objective should always be to simplify the access process, make the conditions uniform for all users and make the facilities as accessible as possible. This ensures that the wider scientific community of users has effective and convenient access to conduct excellent research and guarantees optimal use of RI resources. Development and maintenance of a general access programme with a coordinated timeline, along with the possibility to monitor key performance indicators, would further support these goals.

3 Policy and legal aspects of access

Task 1.2 and the resulting Deliverable 1.2 provided an insight into the common policy and legal framework for distributed RIs in the atmospheric domain, and this unified framework is essential for establishing fair and effective access conditions for the whole atmospheric research community. This document defines a series of recommendations for a common legal framework for access provision, data access and use of services. The key components of a common policy and legal framework include the following:

1. General requirements for users are to be designed in a way to ensure that the infrastructure is used safely, efficiently and effectively, and that the research conducted using the infrastructure is of high quality, has the potential to make a significant contribution to the atmospheric science, and complies with the ethical and legal requirements. A Terms of Use Agreement may be drawn up by the RI to be signed by users to accept the access conditions.
2. The common Data Policy should aim to set the principles for the collection, storage and management of research data. Its goal is to ensure that collected data follow the FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable), are collected and managed ethically, and comply with relevant laws, regulations, and ethical guidelines. The Data Policy should also ensure the integrity, accuracy, and reliability of research data, while facilitating their accessibility for future use. The Data Management Plan along with the Access Management Plan; developed to meet the needs of each RI, should describe the data lifecycle and data management, and the data generated through access and its metadata are to be stored by the RI data centre.
3. The policy on users' personal data should set the guidelines and regulations for the individuals' rights to access and correct their personal information collected and used during the access process. Such policy is supplemented by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) which sets out the rules for the collection, use, handling, storage, deletion and processing of personal data of individuals within the EU. RIs should design the access management process in a way to protect the privacy and confidentiality of all actors participating in the access process, while informing individuals of their GDPR rights.
4. Reporting and Publication Policy should set out the rules and guidelines for researchers and publishers when reporting and disseminating scientific findings to the scientific community and the general public. These policies should ensure that scientific research is conducted and reported in an ethical, transparent, and rigorous manner. Users should be encouraged to make their publications available through open-access repositories and to disseminate the results from their access (except for users from the private

sector). It is essential that the support of the access providing facility and its staff is acknowledged, and even to consider offering co-authorship to those who made significant contributions to the work.

5. Ownership and intellectual property rights should be clearly defined, including third party rights, access rights for the RI, and licensing arrangements.

It is important to acknowledge, however, that establishing a common access policy for various access modalities and across multiple RIs may be rather challenging due to the specific requirements of different facilities and the diversity of the provided services.

For seamless provision of access services, it is important to analyse the legal and managerial needs by the service providers and define the terms for access provision, e.g., through service-level agreements with the access providers.

4 Financial aspects of access

Ensuring financial sustainability of access to atmospheric RIs is crucial in order to keep the RI services open and available to a wide user community, while maintaining financial viability over the long term. Achieving this for distributed RIs requires leveraging a diverse range of stable funding sources and mechanisms for access. The key funding sources for access include

1. National/Regional/Institutional funding – supports construction, core operations, maintenance, staff salaries, sometimes co-funded by EU structural funds.
2. Project funding – EU and national grants (Horizon Europe, INFRA programs) support specific research activities, development of access capabilities, and transnational access (TNA).
3. RI funding – membership contributions from member countries cover core functions, central coordination, data services, training, but rarely fully fund physical/remote access.
4. Other funding – user or service fees, bilateral agreements, or contracts (e.g., ITINERIS, ECMWF) support specific access or services.

Most distributed European RIs, including ERICs, rely on multi-level funding structures, often combining member contributions, national funding, and competitive EU grants. A minority of ERICs explicitly account for physical/remote access in their financial models; service fees are sometimes applied to industry users or non-member researchers. Ensuring sustainable access requires stable combinations of funding and careful alignment of national, EU, and institutional contributions.

In addition, sustainable access requires the consideration of user categories and services, while fostering scientific excellence through competitive and innovative research opportunities. Sustainability also requires implementing a balance between equitable access for a broad user base and an effective pricing strategy. Furthermore, funding and pricing models should also be explored based on the available funding sources, user type (academic vs. non-academic), and user origin (RI member country vs. non-member country). Pricing should remain flexible and account for the possibility of subsidised access for users, e.g., from RI member countries. By adopting a balanced and adaptable approach, the introduction of a pricing scheme will enhance the financial sustainability of RIs while ensuring fair and efficient access to their services. It should be noted that these practices cannot easily be harmonised between the RIs, and they will also depend strongly on the type of access service provided.

Full cost analysis for access provision is critical, even if fixed costs could not be directly charged, to ensure financial transparency, planning, and justification for funding. Cost models should include all relevant operational costs (investment, personnel, consumables, indirect costs) and distinguish between fixed vs. variable costs. In Task 1.3, an initial access cost collector tool was developed to standardize data collection across facilities. Some challenges were encountered during the process, such as difficulty compiling comprehensive equipment lists and depreciation costs; and difficulty distinguishing fixed vs variable costs due to a lack of detailed records. It is important to consider these in future work.

A well-structured and robust pricing framework for service access should be guided by the following key principles that balance cost recovery with flexibility, fairness, and transparency:

1. cost coverage and sustainability, avoiding any potential double funding
2. flexibility in pricing
3. transparency and fairness
4. open science principles and knowledge dissemination
5. periodic evaluation and adaptability

Several funding pathways for users were listed that can be utilised in the development of financial framework for access to atmospheric research infrastructures. These include i) waived or subsidised fees; ii) Free access via external funding; iii) partially subsidised fee; and iv) full access fees.

Even though Horizon Europe-funded trans-national access (TNA) projects will remain important to enable wide and transparent access to the RIs, a financially sustainable access framework must consider additional funding sources, aiming to widen the funding base beyond TNA projects. These could also include e.g. utilising funding opportunities from national access programmes such as ITINERIS [4], and seeking new funders at national or European level.

5 Concluding remarks

ATMO ACCESS WP1 focused on the elements of developing a coherent and sustainable framework for transnational access to distributed atmospheric research infrastructures, that can be challenging. The guidelines presented in this document highlight the essential managerial, policy, legal, and financial elements needed to ensure that access is fair, efficient, and impactful.

The long-term success of access programmes will depend on maintaining a balance between harmonisation and flexibility: harmonisation to ensure transparency, comparability, and fairness across facilities; and flexibility to account for the diversity of services, funding landscapes, and user needs. Clear procedures, robust monitoring through key performance indicators, and continuous dialogue between providers and users will be critical to achieving this balance.

In the long run, an effective and sustainable access system is not only a management exercise but also an investment in scientific excellence, innovation, and collaboration. By simplifying access, securing diverse and stable funding sources, following open science principles, atmospheric research infrastructures can maximise their societal value, strengthen international cooperation, and support future scientific breakthroughs.

6. References

- [1] Deliverable 1.1 "[Report proposing a common access management concept for atmospheric RIs](#)".
- [2] Deliverable 1.2 "[Consolidation of access policies and legal framework for atmospheric research infrastructures](#)".
- [3] Deliverable 1.3 "[Report on identifying the optimal cost model and pricing schemes for distributed research infrastructures](#)".
- [4] ITINERIS project "Empowering Italy's Environmental Future", <https://itineris.cnr.it/>.

